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MINT^{grün} Robotics Lab: Programming Course for Beginners with Elements of Inquiry-Based Learning

D. Golovko¹

Technical University of Berlin
Berlin, Germany

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ABSTRACT

The MINT^{grün} (English: STEM^{green}) orientation program at the Technical University of Berlin is designed to help students who are not sure about their educational path to make an informed decision. Students enroll in the program for two semesters. In this time, they attend regular university courses from the disciplines of their potential interest as well as special MINT^{grün} courses. The latter include so-called project labs where students get first hands-on experiences in the subject according to the concept of inquiry-based learning. No prior knowledge is required. The robotics lab is one of about ten project labs. The objective of the robotics lab is to give students an easy access to coding and basic electronics as they build and program a simple Arduino-based robot. The projects are carried out in teams. The students come up with the topic of their projects themselves. This paper presents the structure of the robotics lab and discusses some specific challenges and considerations that arise for the instructors of this course.

1 INTRODUCTION

Didactic approaches involving active student participation such as inquiry-based learning (IBL) have been gaining popularity. They are often applied at later stages of the university curriculum. Yet their use with undergraduate students has advantages as well. The robotics lab of the MINT^{grün} orientation program at the Technical University of Berlin was designed for students in the first university year who have not yet decided on their degree program (major). Therefore, besides the function of teaching certain skills and competences, the robotics lab also has the function of

¹ Corresponding Author
D. Golovko
d.golovko@tu-berlin.de

introducing the students to coding, electronics and the problem-solving mindset required in engineering. In the following, we present the orientation program and the robotics lab with an emphasis on the elements of IBL.

2 MINT^{GRÜN} ORIENTATION PROGRAM

The orientation program MINT^{grün} (literally translated as “STEM^{green}”, where “green” stands for a focus on sustainability issues) started at the Technical University of Berlin in 2012 and has enjoyed growing popularity [6]. In the academic year 2018/2019, 588 students are enrolled in the program [8].

The program aims at students (predominantly young high-school graduates) who are not sure about their future educational path, e.g. the choice of major or the choice of university studies vs. vocational training. The objective of the MINT^{grün} program is to assist students in making an informed decision about their career choices based on the experience they acquire attending university classes over the course of one year (two semesters). The central idea of the MINT^{grün} program is that in order to decide consciously for or against a major, one needs to try out at least some classes from that field of studies. Furthermore, some students may decide against university studies altogether and e.g. enroll for vocational training. A further objective of MINT^{grün} is the reduction of drop-out rates² in bachelor programs by providing students with a more realistic picture of the demands in a university STEM program and by raising the students' motivation as a result of an informed choice of their major.

Besides about 50 regular courses that students attend from the curriculum of the majors they are interested in, there are additional, MINT^{grün}-specific courses. These are two orientation courses in a lecture format and project laboratories (labs). The credits students receive during the MINT^{grün} year can be transferred to their chosen degree program, similarly to how students who change their majors do.

Depending on the semester, there are around 10 MINT^{grün} labs. They encompass various subjects, e.g. following labs are offered in the summer semester of 2019: construction of mechanical machines [2], environmental issues, mathematical modeling in sciences [1], chemistry [6], physics, robotics, mechatronics, fluid mechanics [7], science and engineering history, ethical and societal issues in engineering and sciences.

² Drop-out rates in Germany's bachelor programs are high with 29% students quitting without a degree. Drop-out rates in sciences and mathematics are the highest at 38% [3].

3 INQUIRY-BASED LEARNING

Most of the MINT^{grün} project labs use the approach of inquiry-based learning (IBL). IBL is a broad term that implies a student-centered teaching format with open problem statements, an emphasis on 'learning to learn' and the process of knowledge acquisition rather than instruction and the knowledge itself, a participative rather than receptive student role, a high degree of students' independence and their active involvement in all stages of elaborating their own solution to the problem [4]. In German-language literature, this didactic approach can also be referred to as research-based learning ("forschendes Lernen"). The robotics lab in particular uses a variation of IBL, the project-based learning (PjBL). This variation is characterized by a learning-by-doing approach, an orientation towards an end product (e.g. a prototype) and teamwork. This learning form originated in engineering and can give students an impression of the ways how practicing engineers work [2].

4 ORGANIZATION OF THE ROBOTICS LAB

The robotics lab is a one-semester course with 6 ECTS. Students (max. 45 students per semester divided into two groups) get the assignment to build and program a simple Arduino-based robot. They work in teams of 2-4 (in rare cases 5) persons and come up with the project ideas themselves. Fig. 1 shows an example of a robot built last semester. Inspired by the film "WALL-E", the robot can ride around the table, detect an object (a yellow or black clump) with a distance sensor, ride towards it, lift it using the arm with an electromagnet and place it into one of the boxes depending on its color.

Fig. 1. Example of a project completed in the robotics lab (prototype by "WALL-E" team)

The semester in the robotics lab is divided into two parts: the introductory phase (first 4-5 weeks) and the project phase (rest of the semester). The introductory phase is a programming crash course. Students, who are assumed to be absolute beginners, need to learn the bare minimum so that they can start working on their projects. In this phase we resort to the format of frontal instruction. Students follow the teacher's instructions in assembling and programming their simple circuits. To keep attention, we have found it helpful to interrupting the lecture style with frequent questions and small practical assignments. We work in Arduino IDE, which uses a simplified version of C++, and Processing, which uses a simplified version of Java. There are weekly home assignments. Additionally, there are tutorials that focus on basic electronics. The weekly classroom presence time is 4+2 contact hours.

The project phase starts with students deciding on the project topics and planning the projects. They have to do so in writing on the course wiki page and include a Gantt chart to illustrate the project schedule. The chart is later used to compare the actual progress of the team with the plan. The project phase ends with an oral presentation and a written documentation of the project in the wiki (see Fig. 2). The latter is publicly accessible [5]. In the project phase, the teams work independently on their projects with the support of the instructors.

Fig. 2. Semester plan

The instructors in the robotics lab currently include a postdoc research assistant (20 hours/week) and two undergraduate student assistants (15+10 hours/week). The involvement of student assistants (tutors) is very beneficial for this interdisciplinary course because it expands the competence field of the instructors if they can join expertise from different professional areas (majors).

The capacity of the robotics lab is 45 students/semester, who are divided into two groups.

The robotics lab implements the major elements of IBL Tab. 1 gives a more detailed overview.

Table 1. Principles of Inquiry-Based Learning and Their Implementation in the Robotics Lab

Principle	Implementation
Authentic problem situations with an open outcome	Students build prototypes according to their own ideas and go through all the stages of the construction process including planning, design, coding, testing and documentation.
Learner-centered activities	Students formulate their project topics and work on them in small teams. However, the introductory phase of the course is in the format of frontal instruction.
Active participation in all stages of a research project, autonomous learning	Students formulate topics, create a project plan, carry out the project and present the results largely on their own
Instructors assume the role of facilitators	In the project phase, the instructors' primary role is answering questions and (upon request) giving tips on how to solve problems that the teams encounter. The introductory phase is teacher-centered. Sometimes more instructors' intervention is necessary, e.g. to influence the group dynamics and the temporal planning of the project.
The learning is process-centered rather than result-centered	Following a solution that eventually proves unsuccessful is not viewed negatively. Students do not receive penalties if the project remains unfinished despite sufficient effort.
Learning centers on acquiring skills and competences rather than knowledge of facts	The course aims at developing the mindset and problem-solving skills required for writing code and similar engineering tasks. Furthermore, students practice teamwork, communication, presentation skills and persistence.
Presentation of results to an interested audience	Students document their projects in a wiki that is publicly accessible. Students hold an oral presentation on their project at the last course meeting.
Critical reflection of the results	Students are required to include a “Discussion” section into their project documentation and critically discuss the project outcomes and the suitability of the chosen solutions. Reflection is welcomed at the oral presentation and during conversations with instructors within the team.

Robotics lab enjoys popularity among students, which can be explained by the fun factor (robots) and the fact that programming skills are part of many university majors and professions. Since there are usually more MINT^{grün} students willing to take the course than places available, almost all of the places are allocated to MINT^{grün} students. If students of higher semesters do take part in the course, MINT^{grün} students get the opportunity to exchange ideas and acquire more information about the majors of these older students.

In the last 4 semesters, 160 students started the course (i.e. participated in the first meeting), 129 started teamwork (i.e. stayed until the 5h week) and 110 stayed until the end. In the survey at the end of the course, over 90% of the students assess the course as “good” or “very good” and claim they would recommend it to others. It should, however, be noted that those who dropped out did not participate in the survey.

5 CHALLENGES

1. *Supervision load.* New, open-outcome project topics imply that the instructors have to obtain at least a basic idea of the methods, components etc. that can be used in the projects. This can be time-consuming since the projects are quite different each semester. However, it is often not needed that the instructors are informed about the solutions to a great detail. Instead, it makes sense that the instructors explain the students how they would proceed to solve the problem (even if they don't know if that is the right approach) rather than presenting the students with a ready answer. E.g. when it comes to bug fixing, the instructors will typically not be familiar with the individual projects to the degree of detail that allows an immediate solution, but it can be useful to point out the thought process and suggest how the problem can be narrowed down to several most likely causes and those can be identified and ruled out or corrected one by one.

This hands-on, non-frontal teaching formats requires a relatively high instructor-to-student ratio. The lab has 40-45 students in the beginning and 25-30 students in the end of the course, which results in more than 10 teams per semester. The biggest bottlenecks timewise are grading the homework, and preparing for the project supervision, i.e. researching and trying out the methods and components that can be used in the individual projects. In the course of the semester, the biggest load for the instructors is at the beginning of the project phase, when the students have selected their project topics and the homework still needs to be graded.

2. *Varying prior knowledge.* Even though the course is designed for absolute beginners, there are always a few students who have already taken programming classes or even have experience with Arduino. They can be somewhat bored during the introductory phase. One way to make them maintain interest is to interrupt the lecture teaching style with frequent questions, which they may be able to answer. For very advanced students, giving additional tasks (e.g. operating a particular component) to solve during class may be a solution. In the project phase, these

students can assume more complex tasks that challenge them. Because students do not all perform same tasks, like it is usually the case with more traditional teaching methods, this approach can accommodate the students' varying knowledge more easily.

3. *Transition from introductory to project phase.* Some students are overwhelmed by having to formulate the project idea, find the team and participate in the course in a much more active manner than during the frontal instruction phase. In the current semester, we try to ease the transition by making the students pick their ideas and teams early in the introductory phase. The expectation is that this way, the students have several weeks to think the idea through, to get acquainted with their team or perhaps to even change teams.

4. *Team work.* The group dynamics in the course is not always satisfactory. In some teams, students are tempted to divide the workload in the team into construction (mostly designing, cutting and assembling the robot wooden frame) and coding. Students that have some prior programming experience will typically take over the latter. If the roles do not change throughout the semester, then those who did the construction tasks will not have gained coding experience. Furthermore, the construction tasks only play an auxiliary role in the course because the robotics lab lacks both sophisticated implements and instructors' competence to teach valuable skills to students in that field. The preferred division of labor is a functional one, where students make sure certain robot functions are implemented, which involves both the construction and coding (e.g. mounting and programming a particular sensor or motor). The instructors' repeated intervention is therefore necessary for some teams. Sometimes it is hard to convince students to change the distribution of roles in the team.

Smaller teams tend to have better group dynamics and often accomplish more work than larger ones. Reasons are less organisational overhead and fewer opportunities for free-riding.

Group work may be a more suitable learning format for some students than for others depending on their personality type, communication skills, social role in the group, maturity and previous experience, etc. [2].

5. *Grading.* Fair grading is a challenge because the projects vary in their complexity and the degree of completion and the students start the course with different prior knowledge. IBL focuses on the inquiry process rather than the end result. This should be reflected in the grading procedure. It is helpful to create rubrics that evaluate aspects of students' performance that are independent of the chosen project topics. However, a lot of subjectivity remains in the grading process.

6 DISCUSSION

The challenges listed above are not unique to the robotics lab. Similar issues have been described by other authors practicing IBL or PjBL [2, 4].

Despite the interest towards active learning formats in the recent years, IBL is sometimes considered to be more suitable for students at more advanced stages of university education (e.g. master thesis). However, courses using the format of IBL work well at the initial stages too. This applies especially for topics where the necessary minimum of prior knowledge can be acquired in the short time and students can proceed to working hands-on on their projects. A programming course that uses mostly procedural programming is very suitable in this respect.

In the context of orientation studies, IBL is attractive because it lets students get a feel of hands-on work in the field without having to attend several semesters of theoretical courses on the fundamentals of the academic discipline they are interested in. Furthermore, even if the students decide against studying that discipline, the practical skills acquired during the course (e.g. coding, problem solving) can be helpful in their further lives. This goes along with the goal of the Bologna declaration to increase the students' employability.

Coding is sometimes viewed as a challenging, problematic skill that is hard to acquire but required in most STEM disciplines. If the first experiences with coding were positive, this can give the students more confidence to choose a STEM major that they are interested in but fear the complexity.

It should be noted that courses like the robotics lab are not a substitute for more theory-centered classes as well as programming classes that teach more advanced use of programming language(s) than the relatively limited Arduino IDE can foster. It can be useful to point this out to students, especially if they plan to make their decision about their further studies based on the attendance of the lab. Yet such practice-oriented courses early on in the university curriculum can give students a feel of hands-on work in the corresponding discipline and put the more advanced theoretical knowledge into a context.

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